

Afghanistan Economic Challenges: Post 15 August 2021

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Abstract: The aim of this study was to explore the challenges faced by the economy of Afghanistan, after the 15th of August 2021 political changes in the country and its consequences and as well the possible solutions for mitigating the emerged challenges. For meeting the study objectives, cross-sectional qualitative research genre was adopted, where a sample size of 13 information rich participants was interviewed for the data collection, through in-depth interview approach. The interviews' digital records were subsequently transcribed verbatim and translated from Pashto and Dari into English language. The interviews' data was then coded, analyzed and interpreted thematically, as a result, three main themes were identified: 'Afghanistan's economy is facing Multi-dimensional challenges, due to the imposed sanctions', 'Afghanistan will face Economic Depression coupled with political and social instability if the current Problems are not solved', 'Crafting effective Political plus Economic Policies both at National and International Levels are required'. The imposed sanctions and absence of International Recognition of the current government in power were considered most significant challenges to be affecting the economy of Afghanistan.

Keywords: Economic Crisis, Post-Conflict Economy, Thematic Analysis, Afghanistan Economy, Political Instability, Economic Challenges

1. Introduction

The 15th of August 2021 political changes in Afghanistan which was followed by a massive economic decline in many sectors, coupled with humanitarian and financial crisis in the country, took an already fragile and weak economy to the brink of collapse and back for generations, which was already struggling with adverse shocks of COVID-19, droughts and insecurity. Whereas, 98 percent of the population is facing food insecurity and are unable to consume enough (Rappler, 2021), further, 97% of the population is estimated by UNDP (2021) to sink below the poverty line by 2022, as the surging inflation and devaluation of AFN currency, that was never recorded during the past two decades prior to August 2021 in the country is driving more people into poverty and food insecurity. There has been a significant increase in the unemployment rate in the country as well, with businesses and NGOs closed, compounded with the job losses of a total estimated 500,000 National Security Forces members of the previous Afghan government and the restrictions on the employment of women, where women form half of the Afghan population and their unemployment can cause 5 percent contraction in the GDP of Afghanistan according to UNDP (2021). Main while, there has been major layoffs in most of the businesses that are still open in the country and getting near to collapse, which is further negatively impacting the dire economic and humanitarian situation, adding up to unemployment rate in the country. The banking sector was severely hit by the liquidity crisis coupled with high demand for cash withdrawals from the banks by the depositors since after the August 2021 developments in the country.

If the imposed sanctions are not removed and the liquidity crisis is not solved, banks are going to collapse in Afghanistan with an already confidence crisis among the Afghan

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population towards the banking sector. There is further the crisis of immigration, where young and mostly educated population of the country are leaving and taking refuge or seeking asylum in other countries, further causing brain drain in the country, with hundreds more applying daily for passports and visas in capital Kabul and other provinces across the country, which is not only negatively affecting the economy of Afghanistan, but is also contributing to the refugee crisis in the neighboring countries and other countries around the world as a whole, especially the European states. According to Baloch et al (2017), the influx of Afghan refugees has been among the main factors for the economic instability in Pakistan. There is also report of 50-70 percent decrease in Trade Volume of the country after the August 2021 political changes in Afghanistan (TOLO, 2021).

In the course of Afghanistan's history, there has been conflicts and wars since for decades and it will mostly be rare to find times of economic stability, welfare and prosperity, as Afghanistan has been the battleground for the world empires and superpowers coupled with its own domestic challenges. Often the natural resources have been referred to as the main reason of all these havoc and devastations, to the extent that, the colonial states have tried every possible means for getting their hands onto the untapped natural resources of Afghanistan. Where the large body of literatures documented on the direct impacts of conflicts and wars over the economic growth and development of countries around the world, with some of them reviewed in this research project- shows that, there always have been negative and adverse impacts of conflicts on the economy and living conditions of affected people during and post conflict periods, with consequences such as; destroyed physical and human capital of countries, economic collapse or slowdown in growth, humanitarian crisis, and displacements. The USIP (2012) has called Afghanistan a rentier state through the history, as Afghanistan has relied on foreign aid back from the eighteenth century and during the British empire in the nineteenth century all the way to the Soviet Union and U.S. and its allies.

According to Karimi et al (2021), Afghanistan GDP had an unstable growth rate since from 1970s till 2014 due to the unprecedented events, and after 2014 Afghanistan maintained an average constant GDP growth rate of +2.2 percent. Another study by Joya (2011) discusses that, the unstable economic growth in Afghanistan for the past 4 decades have multiple reasons behind, which includes: macroeconomic volatility, reliance on foreign aid, civil wars, being a Land Lock Country, weak institutions, corruption, and some sociocultural barriers.

1.1. Afghanistan Economic Challenges during 1979 – 2001

Due to weak states and being a resource-poor country throughout the history have induced and made the economic development a difficult process in Afghanistan, where conflicts between 1979 and 2001 caused huge devastations and turmoil in Afghanistan beside the destroyed physical capital, it had left negative impacts on human capital as well, where the Infant mortality rates had increased, healthcare system was collapsed, heavy migration had occurred due to which skilled labour left the country, including doctors and nurses among the migrants and later women were segregated by removing them of their employment and studying rights, which in return had negatively impacted the health sector (Roy, 2020). During those periods there was high rate of informal economy and low domestic revenues, as the regions, especially the countryside were not integrated by the central government and the warlords had control over the land trade ports, there was dependence on foreign aid for covering the expenditures, as according to Nijssen (2010) during the 1950 and 1970 Soviet Union provided 50 percent and U.S. 30 percent aid to Afghanistan, agriculture sector was the only source for income. Another study by Eltezam (2015) discusses that, during 1907 Britain was providing 400,000 Pounds Sterling aid each year until 1919 to the

Afghan government for covering up its expenditures, where back then India was the principle trade partner and then the Russia. 94
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1.2. Afghanistan Economic Challenges during 2002 – 2020 96

After the decades conflicts and wars, the process of rebuilding infrastructures in Afghanistan started with the support of International community especially U.S. and its allies in 2002, where new jobs were created in vast numbers, school-aged population started going to schools including girls, the collapsed healthcare system was rehabilitated, where skilled foreign labour came to the country, migration rate started to drop, people gained access to water and electricity, highways, roads, and streets were paved (asphalted), banking system started to operate in the country, water control and management projects were started, economy started to grow. But, after the 2012 International troops withdrawal from Afghanistan the economy growth saw slowdown, where investments and expenditures dropped, and there were deep structural problems, the government was not able to integrate the regions under one rule. Despite the support from NATO and especially the U.S, trafficking and opium cultivation continued, the economy was not diversified, where agriculture and industrial sectors were not a sustainable economic growth means, insurgency was threatening every sector, the economic growth depended on the services sector despite the jobs insecurity and low-payment in this sector, inequality and poverty increased, economic growth concentrated in cities only, inequality between countryside and towns grew wider, unemployment increased after the withdrawal, and amidst all these uncertainties in Afghanistan, the COVID-19 even hit the country hard (Roy, 2020). 97
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2. Methodology 115

This study employs qualitative research genre, where researchers have used inductive approach, seeking to investigate and explore the Economic Challenges faced by Afghanistan after the 15 of August 2021 political changes in the country, its consequences and possible solutions. 116
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2.1. Study Population and Sample 120

The target population for this study was information rich cases, with their studies and expertise in economic related fields and who were engaged in the economic sectors of Afghanistan. Researchers have interviewed a purposeful sample of 13 information rich participants, because of their studies and professional background in economic field, since these aspects exposes them to rich information about economics in a wider scale and develops their understandings about its trends and problems. Majority of the participants were Kabul-based Economic lecturers from different prominent Higher Education Universities, and rest were from the government banking and other economic sectors. The participants anonymity was ensured while reporting the results. 121
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2.2. Data Collection Procedure 130

In this study, researchers have used in-depth interview approach, where one participant was interviewed online, and the rest were interviewed in person. The interview objectives and questions were shared with the participants in advance, and then the researchers interviewed each case separately. The interviews were all digitally recorded and was then transcribed verbatim; Participants answered the Interview questions in their local languages (Pashto and Dari) where applicable, and was then translated into English. Subsequently the transcribed data was then analyzed using thematic analysis approach. 131
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2.3. Data Analysis Technique 138

Thematic analysis approach was adopted by the researchers for analyzing the interviews’ data, where first all interviews’ digital records were transcribed verbatim and simultaneously translated from Dari and Pashto languages into English, yielding 69 pages and similarly, quotes were also extracted that supported the assertions. Later, the interviews’ transcripts were coded in Ms. Excel using the In Vivo and Causation coding techniques for the first coding cycle, and subsequently in the second coding cycle, the Pattern and Theoretical coding techniques were used – consequently, themes were identified.

3. Analysis and Results

3.1 Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis approach was used for identifying and constructing themes from the Interviews data, primarily supporting the main objectives and questions of this study for exploring the economic challenges, its consequences and possible solutions after the 15 August 2021 political changes in Afghanistan, where three themes were yielded.

This section may be divided by subheadings. It should provide a concise and precise description of the experimental results, their interpretation, as well as the experimental conclusions that can be drawn.

Table 1: Theme 1

<i>Theme-1</i>	<i>Afghanistan’s Economy is facing multi-dimensional Challenges due to The Imposed Sanctions</i>			
<i>Sub-Themes</i>	1	2	3	4
	Financial Crisis	Economic Recession	Socio-Economic Crisis	Political Crisis

The participants have described Afghanistan’s economic challenges to be rooted back into the imposed sanctions to a large scale, and to be multi-dimensional in its essence, which all took place in a parallel form after the 15 of August 2021 power shift in the country, coupled with the withdrawal of all International forces, in specific the U.S and its allies, and the suspension of all International monetary support to the country. due to which the economic, political and social circumstances of the country and its people rigorously turned towards catastrophes and devastations. Where the participants have described the emergent challenges as: i) Financial Crisis ii), Economic Crisis, iii), Socio-Economic crisis, iv) Political Crisis.

3.1.1. Financial Crisis

Participants have indicated during their interviews that, after the political changes in the country, Afghanistan financial institutions faced liquidity crunch, mainly the Central Bank and the Private Banks accordingly, as one of the participants stated:

“the root cause for the banking crisis was the dollars liquidity crunch in the market and with the central bank, while the AFN currency was available in a larger amount, due to which the exchange rate fluctuated.”

Where also a total of \$9.2 billion of DAB Foreign Exchange reserves were frozen, indicating imposed sanctions on the financial sector of the country, similarly all international funds and aids which were provided to the previous government were suspended,

which covered a larger portion of the expenditures and employees' salaries budget of the government; currency circulation also stopped, which was somehow due to the decrease in peoples' consumption triggered by the unemployment and surging prices, further negatively affecting the economic activities in the country, as a participant addressed:

"The AFN currency circulation stopped in such a way that everyone went to the banks and withdrew their deposits and kept it at home."

Economy also suffered from the capital flight, investors and people started to migrate out of the country with their capital and investments and only a handful of the large investors or whose investments were still left in the country, they started to shrank their investments through laying off employees and decreasing their productions capacity, as one of the participants stated that:

"if I am leaving the country or another employee is leaving, then there is no issue with it, but if the main investor or my boss who is a wholesaler and so many individuals are working for him, and those individuals are making their livings out of their jobs, and now if this main investor is leaving, then that is making an issue and would affect me for sure"

due to all the aforementioned factors, AFN currency lost its value against the U.S dollar in the market; there was bank panic immediately, where people started withdrawing their deposits from the banks, as the confidence was lost among the people on the banking system, further most of the banks went bankrupted and as a whole banks came to the precipice of collapsing, on the other hand, International banking operations and services like Western Union and Money Gram services deteriorated.

3.1.2. Economic Recession

Participants during their interviews have indicated that, currently Afghanistan is going through Economic Recession state triggered by the August 2021 changes in the country. as National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) has defined Recession to be the negative growth of GDP for two consecutive quarters. Similarly, that is the case with the economy of Afghanistan, as there is huge contraction or decrease in the GDP; enterprise and small businesses activities have deteriorated rigorously, further causing decrease in production, increasing the unemployment rate and loss of income, as one of the participants described:

"when people stop their consumption, then Alokozay would produce for whom, MTN would provide services to whom, Azizi Bank would operate on the deposits of whom?"

there is also banking crisis with dysfunction in its activities; exchange rates are unstable; there is also loss of confidence both among investors and people, as they are uncertain about their future and their investments, as a participant addressed that:

"What work was done during the past 20 years are not going to happen in just three years and so, and would require approximately the same time span to take place, but we're saying that if it is not going to happen soon enough, then at least some hope must be given to people that, in Future the economy will be in a good position"

and thus, following the mass unemployment across the country both in service and government sectors, which further triggered loss of income and decreased the purchasing power of people. Consequently, people started to decrease their consumptions and spending, which in return negatively affected both the supply and production, as two of the participants described that:

"people got unemployed, government employees lost their jobs and are now using their savings and are trying either to find a job for themselves, or to migrate from the country"

Inflation rate has also increased, for instance, the prices for fuels, food staples, transportation and health services have surged to their highest rates ever compared to the past

two decades, resulting from the AFN currency devaluation, which has mainly affected the prices of import commodities, as Afghanistan is an import dependent country and has been in negative trade balance since the past two decades and even prior to that as well. On the other hand, domestic and international Banking activities have all been deteriorated due to the lack of liquidity and international financial transactions, as one of the participants recalled that:

“there is a friend of mine and he was doing trade with Chinese companies, the other day he told me that, he had ordered six containers of utensils in China, and now the Chinese factory is charging him \$10,000 only for its warehousing, and he is unable to do TT from the banks in Afghanistan to that company in China, which is increasing the cost for him”

3.1.3. Socio-Economic Crisis

Participants have addressed that, due to the political shift in the country and amidst the emergent uncertainties among the people, and subsequently due to the economic shocks, most of the people and in specific the skilled and technical human capital migrated from the country, which in return caused brain drain and in specific a vacuum of skilled human capital in the country, as one of the participants stated that:

“I’ve lost a specialized doctor, and if now I want to have another specialized doctor like him /her, I would need to work for eight more years”

Further, with the exacerbating poverty rate across the country, which is presumed to have colossal negative impacts on the economy and life of people, as for instance, access to education and primarily to good quality education will decrease among the people, especially among the female population. as one of the participants stated:

“While women form half of the Afghanistan population, and if their education is not promoted then there won’t be overall improvement in the economy”

and when education is affected then it means that consequently all other economic sectors will also be affected negatively. As for instance, where the required skilled human capital will be hired from? Meanwhile, there is confidence loss among the people as a whole, if it is on the banking sector, their future, the political system, their access to education, employment, access to basic services, etc. people are in complete despair and anxiety. There is also negative demand shock, as consumption and spending of people have decreased due to multiple reasons, like: unemployment, inflation, and income loss which is also causing financial stress among the people as most of the population is spending their savings since the changes happened, as one of the participants stated as such:

“I spent 50% of my savings during the COVID-19 lockdown, and the amount I’m left with, I’m still spending that now, and if I lose my job then I don’t have any choice but to migrate”

While this is negatively affecting the economic activities in the country, it is also further causing decrease in the circulation of currency in the market. The challenges which unfolded after the August 2021 phenomena in the country, and where people lost their jobs and income sources, psychological and mental disorders are assumed to increase among the people, further affecting their health, as a participant signified this as such:

“there are mental problems nowadays, as if you sit with people anywhere, then you will find them saying that, Afghanistan is in crisis and situation is getting worse with each passing day”

where people will also face acute food insecurity due to the poverty and other aforementioned factors. People will also suffer from lack of access to proper health services across the country as for now most of the healthcare sector staff have either left the country or their salaries are not paid. With all these problems- uncertainty, despair and immigration will increase further; confidence crisis among entrepreneurs and investors will also grow due to the political and economic instability in the country. as a participant stated:

“the entrepreneurs’ confidence is lost and are not willing to do any business, and if they’re not doing business then there won’t be employment, economy will not function”

As the suspension of projects funding by the international community and primarily The World Bank and IMF, which previously had helped initiating large and small national projects, like; construction of roads, school buildings, health centers, water dams, water canals and other such public welfare infrastructures across the country have all come to stop, which had positive impacts on the living conditions of people. And a large number of people were busy working in those projects and were meeting up their basic needs from the wages they received.

3.1.4. Political Crisis

Participants have indicated that, the imposed political sanctions and the absence of International relations and Recognition is the prime cause to all other catastrophes and crisis in the country, coupled with the absence of effective policies implementation by the de-facto government of Afghanistan for working out to get all these challenges and problems solved. As one of the participants stated that:

“Nowadays there are economic challenges in the country and the reason for those challenges are the political challenges”

Table 2: Theme 2

<i>Theme-2</i>	<i>Crafting effective Political plus Economic Policies both at National and International Levels are required</i>	
<i>Sub-Themes</i>	1	2
	Economic Policies	Political Policies

Saving the economy of Afghanistan from the current free fall and further devastations and crises, the participants have proposed that, the government needs to set and adopt strong and effective policies both for its International Relations, National Reconciliation and Peace-Building and economic recovery.

3.1.5 Economic Policies

For the economic policies, participants indicated that current de-facto government needs to set Fiscal, Monetary, Trade and Entrepreneurship policies, so the economy could start to recover. Where, government should increase its expenditures; provide subsidies and its support to the domestic productions and increase tariffs on those goods which are produced domestically, where this will increase domestic revenues, income, and employment rates, meanwhile, Afghanistan will be self-reliant with its own productive economy. Also, there should be control over the Money Exchange Markets to prevent money laundering and foreign exchange currencies illegal outflow, and the U.S dollars should only be used for trade purposes, where a participant noted:

“What I have to do with the dollar as a common citizen, to buy and sell it?”

beside all these, financial institutions must be supported by the government.

3.1.6 Political Policies

Both for the National and International Relations purposes, government must adopt national reconciliation and peacebuilding policies, for which they must also retain the previous government employees, and must work to restore public confidence as a whole. And further for the regional and international relations, it should work for such policies

where it could start restoring effective international relations and gain reliability among the international community, which would then help with the Recognition, and must further get engaged in positive and effective regional cooperation with the neighboring countries. As a participant noted that:

“this problem is political and thus requires political solution, and the economic policies won’t work till then, which requires ten to fifteen years to work. the solution to all these current problems is Recognition of the government currently in power, or compromising with the International community”

Likewise, another participant described that:

“in the current world the winner is the one who has most allies both from economic and political perspectives”

Table 3: Theme 3

<i>Theme-3</i>	<i>Afghanistan will face Economic Depression coupled with political and social instability if the current Problems are not solved</i>
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Participants have addressed and indicated that, in case these challenges are not overcome and solved, their consequences will be colossal, as they presumed that, there will be economic depression, as the GDP will decrease further with increasing unemployment rate, there will be further income loss, no investments will be taking place, trade volume will decrease further, there will be no revenues, Inflation rate will increase more due to which purchasing power of the people will also decrease at the same time, as there will be no employment and income, economic activities will also decrease as a result. As one of the participants described that:

“assume that today I’m paid my salary, I would then go to the market and buy tea, sugar, wheat and what else I might need, and then the retailer will similarly go to the wholesaler to get what he needs, and the same the wholesaler will reach out to the producer. And while I am not buying from the retailer, he won’t reach out to the wholesaler and the same is the case between the wholesaler and producer. So, economy paralyzes and stagnates, where eventually producer will stop production and will lay off some of the labour force, which will then cause unemployment.”

Further, there will be severe financial crisis, where AFN currency will lose its value and would be the same old decades AFN currency. On the other hand, social instability and crime rates will increase due to increase in the poverty and unemployment, as one of the participants stated;

“when someone is dying out of hunger, then that person will not consider humanity nor the Islam, that person would only ponder on how to survive”

there will be severe psychological and mental issues growing among the people; illegal migration will be happening; there will be no skilled human capital left in the country; Education and school attending rates will decrease among the people; there will be chances for terrorist and hostile groups to breed and recruit; political instability will grow

and the economy will be informal to a large extent, and Afghanistan will be a consumer market of other countries. 364
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4. Discussion 366

This qualitative study was undertaken to explore the challenges faced by the economy of Afghanistan after the 15th of August 2021 political shift in the country. The findings show that, political instability, colonial statecrafts, foreign interventions, inequality, cultural barriers, unintegrated regions, lack of national unity, reliance of Afghan government throughout the history on foreign aids, and beside all these, due to decades of war, conflicts, lack of proper economic infrastructures, the geographic location, weak states, resources scarcity, and lack of technological innovations, all together have pushed the economy of Afghanistan into a dark circle since from decades to date. 367
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This study findings show that, the economy of Afghanistan is facing multi-dimensional challenges, negatively affecting its economy and living conditions of its people after the political changes of 15-August 2021 in the country. Where the imposed sanctions and political instability were considered as the main negative factors, and substantial drivers for economic, humanitarian, financial, social and political crisis in the country, both among the participants and the reviewed literatures. The past two decades have proven that, if regional integration and national reconciliation with peacebuilding are not achieved and implemented, things will still end up in devastations, and catastrophes- no matter how much time, efforts and money are being spent. 375
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Further the findings show that, Afghanistan will face the fate of impoverished African states, with grim economic, social, and political consequences, in case the emerged problems are not solved, as there will be economic depression plus a disconnected and abandoned nation to its own fate, in a global village with no relations. For the economy of Afghanistan to recover, primarily it is required for the government to adopt effective international and national level policies for achieving its credibility and recognition among the international community, and domestic legitimacy. 384
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It is required for the current government in power to show flexibility, recruit technical experts and work towards crafting comprehensive set of consolidated and coordinated fiscal, monetary, national and international relations policies- which will make the economic recovery possible and subsequently will avert further devastations and catastrophes from happening. It is required utmost for the current government in power to work towards achieving public confidence, and credence among the international community. Otherwise, there will be colossal economic catastrophes, legal and illegal immigration will both increase, poverty rate will also increase further and consequently these factors will nurture miseries among the people and Afghan society, and would ultimately cause calamities such as; economic crisis, financial crisis, social crisis and political crisis. Further, it is required for the international community U.S in specific to engaged with the Taliban as they are the last resort for Afghanistan. 391
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